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SATYAM COMPUTER SCAM – PRE AND POST DIAGNOSIS

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ABSTRACT

Scandals are often the “**tip of the iceberg**”. They represent the ‘**visible**’ catastrophic failures. An attempt is made in this paper to examine in-depth and analyze India’s Enron, Satyam Computer’s “**creative-accounting**” scandal. Their scandal/fraud has put a big question mark on the entire corporate governance system in India. In public companies, this type of ‘creative’ accounting leading to fraud and investigations are, therefore, launched by the various governmental oversight agencies. The accounting fraud committed by the founders of Satyam in 2009 is a testament to the fact that “the science of conduct is swayed in large by human greed, ambition, and hunger for power, money, fame and glory.” Scandals have proved that “there is an urgent need for good conduct based on strong corporate governance, ethics and accounting & auditing standards.” Unlike Enron, which sank due to ‘agency’ problem, Satyam was brought to its knee due to ‘tunneling’ effect. The Satyam scandal highlights the importance of securities laws and CG in emerging markets. Indeed, Satyam fraud “spurred the government of India to tighten the CG norms to prevent recurrence of similar frauds in future.” Thus, major financial reporting frauds need to be studied for ‘lessons-learned’ and ‘strategies-to-follow’ to reduce the incidents of such frauds in the future. The increasing rate of white-collar crimes “demands stiff penalties, exemplary punishments, and effective enforcement of law with the right spirit.”

Keywords: Corporate accounting scandal, Satyam Computer India, corporate governance, Accounting and auditing standards.

Issues:

- » Study the corporate governance structure that existed at Satyam Computers.
- » Appreciate the importance of Code of Conduct and Whistleblower policy of a Company.
- » Examine the roles and responsibilities of a company's board and independent directors.
- » Critically analyze the instances where the independent directors failed to fulfill their responsibilities.
- » Understand the limitations of independent directors in Satyam's case.

Background Note:

Satyam Computer Services Ltd was founded in 1987 by B. Ramalinga Raju. The company offers information technology (IT) services spanning various sectors, and is listed on the New York Stock Exchange and Euro next. Satyam's network covers 67 countries across six

continents. The company employs 40,000 IT professionals across development centers in India, the United States, the United Kingdom, the United Arab Emirates, Canada, Hungary, Singapore, Malaysia, China, Japan, Egypt and Australia. It serves over 654 global companies, 185 of which are Fortune 500 corporations. Satyam has strategic technology and marketing alliances with over 50 companies. Apart from Hyderabad, it has development centers in India at Bangalore, Chennai, Pune, Mumbai, Nagpur, Delhi, Kolkata, Bhubaneswar, and Visakhapatnam. "The truth is as old as the hills" opined Mahatma Gandhi, christened the Father of the Nation by Indians. So a company named "Satyam" (Truth, in Sanskrit) inspired trust.

The IT boom in India, was fuelled by young, middle-class, and educated, budding Indian entrepreneurs and Western firms anxious to outsource to take advantage of high-skill, low-wage worker. This trend created a new breed of businessmen for the 21st century and generated many fortunes literally overnight. The global corporate community was flabbergasted and scandalized when the Chairman of Satyam, Mr. Ramalinga Raju resigned on 7th January, 2009 and confessed that he had manipulated the accounts by \$1.47-billion.

Emergence of Satyam Computer Services:

Satyam Computer Services Limited was a 'rising-star' in the Indian 'outsourced' IT-services industry. The company was formed in 1987 in Hyderabad (India) by Mr. Ramalinga Raju. The firm began with 20 employees and grew rapidly as a 'global' business. It offered IT and business process outsourcing (BPO) services spanning various sectors. Satyam was as an example of "India's growing success." Satyam won numerous awards for innovation, governance, and corporate accountability. As Agrawal and Sharma (2009) states, "In 2007, Ernst & Young awarded Mr. Raju with the 'Entrepreneur of the Year' award. On April 14, 2008, Satyam won awards from MZ Consult's for being a 'leader in India in CG and accountability'. In September 2008, the World Council for Corporate Governance awarded Satyam with the 'Global Peacock Award' for global excellence in corporate accountability." Unfortunately, less than five months after winning the Global Peacock Award, Satyam became the centerpiece of a 'massive' accounting fraud. By 2003, Satyam's IT services businesses included 13,120 technical associates servicing over 300 customers worldwide. At that time, the world-wide IT services market was estimated at nearly \$400 billion, with an estimated annual compound growth rate of 6.4%. "The markets major drivers at that point in time were the increased importance of IT services to businesses world-wide; the impact of the Internet on e Business; the emergence of a high-quality IT services industry in India and their methodologies; and, the growing need of IT services providers who could provide a range of services." To effectively compete, both against domestic and global competitors, the company embarked on a variety of multi-pronged business growth strategies

Mr. Ramalinga Raju and the Satyam Scandal:

On January 7, 2009, Mr. Raju disclosed in a letter, as shown to Satyam Computers Limited Board of Directors that "he had been manipulating the company's accounting numbers for years." Mr. Raju claimed that he overstated assets on Satyam's balance sheet by \$1.47 billion. Nearly \$1.04 billion in bank loans and cash that the company claimed to own was non-existent. Satyam also underreported liabilities on its balance sheet. Satyam overstated

income nearly every quarter over the course of several years in order to meet analyst expectations. For example, the results announced on October 17, 2009 overstated quarterly revenues by 75 percent and profits by 97 percent. Mr. Raju and the company's global head of internal audit used a number of different techniques to perpetrate the fraud.

As Ramachandran (2009) pointed out, "Using his personal computer, Mr. Raju created numerous bank statements to advance the fraud. Mr. Raju falsified the bank accounts to inflate the balance sheet with balances that did not exist. He inflated the income statement by claiming interest income from the fake bank accounts. Mr. Raju also revealed that he created 6,000 fake salary accounts over the past few years and appropriated the money after the company deposited it. The company's global head of internal audit created fake customer identities and generated fake invoices against their names to inflate revenue.

The global head of internal audit also forged board resolutions and illegally obtained loans for the company." It also appeared that the cash that the company raised through American Depository Receipts in the United States never made it to the balance sheets

Operating Performance of Satyam:

Table-1 "Operating Performance"

Particulars	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	Average Growth Rate (%)
Net Sales	25,415.40	34,642.20	46,343.10	62,284.70	81,372.80	38
Operating Profit	7,743.00	9,717.00	15,714.20	17,107.30	20,857.40	28
Net Profit	5,557.90	7,502.60	12,397.50	14,232.30	17,157.40	33
Operating Cash Flow	4,165.50	6,386.60	7,868.10	10,390.60	13,708.70	35
ROCE (%)	27.95	29.85	31.34	31.18	29.57	30
ROE (%)	23.57	25.88	26.85	28.14	26.12	26

Source- Based on Scholar Work

CONFESSIONS OF RAJU:

1. Inflated (non-existent) cash and bank balances of Rs 5,040 crore (as against Rs 5,361 crore reflected in the books) on the balance sheet as of September 30, 2008.
2. An accrued interest of Rs 376 crore which is non-existent.
3. An understated liability of Rs 1,230 crore on account of funds.
4. An overstated debtors position of Rs 490 crore (as against Rs 2,651 reflected in the books).

5. For the September quarter, Satyam frequently reported a revenue of Rs 2,700 crore and an operating margin of Rs 649 crore (24% of revenues) as against the actual revenues of Rs 2,112 crore and an actual operating margin of Rs 61 crore (3% of revenues).

This has resulted in artificial cash and bank balances going up by Rs 588 crore in Q2 alone.

Raju acknowledged that the gap in the balance sheet had arisen on account of inflated profits over a period of last several years.

Satyam's Founder, Chairman and CEO, Mr. Raju's Letter to his Board of Directors

To The Board of Directors,

Satyam Computer Services Ltd.

From: B. Ramalinga Raju

Chairman, Satyam Computer Services Ltd.

January 7, 2009

Dear Board Members,

It is with deep regret, and tremendous burden that I am carrying on my conscience, that I would like to bring the following facts to your notice:

1. The Balance Sheet carries as of September 30, 2008:

- (a) Inflated (non-existent) cash and bank balances of Rs.5, 040 crore (as against Rs. 5,361 crore reflected in the books);
- (b) An accrued interest of Rs. 376 crore which is non-existent;
- (c) An understated liability of Rs. 1,230 crore on account of funds arranged by me; and
- (d) An over stated debtor's position of Rs. 490 crore (as against Rs. 2,651 reflected in the books).

2. For the September quarter (Q2), we reported a revenue of Rs.2, 700 crore and an operating margin of Rs. 649 crore (24% of revenues) as against the actual revenues of Rs. 2,112 crore and an actual operating margin of Rs. 61 Crore (3% of revenues). This has resulted in artificial cash and bank balances going up by Rs. 588 crore in Q2 alone. The gap in the Balance Sheet has arisen purely on account of inflated profits over a period of last several years (limited only to Satyam standalone, books of subsidiaries reflecting true performance). What started as a marginal gap between actual operating profit and the one reflected in the books of accounts continued to grow over the years. It has attained unmanageable proportions as the size of company operations grew significantly (annualized revenue run rate of Rs. 11,276 crore in the September quarter, 2008 and official reserves of Rs. 8,392 crore).

The differential in the real profits and the one reflected in the books was further accentuated by the fact that the company had to carry additional resources and assets to justify higher level of operations —thereby significantly increasing the costs. Every attempt made to eliminate the gap failed. As the promoters held a small percentage of equity, the concern was that poor performance would result in a take-over, thereby exposing the gap. It was like

riding a tiger, not knowing how to get off without being eaten. The aborted Maytas acquisition deal was the last attempt to fill the fictitious assets with real ones. Maytas' investors were convinced that this is a good divestment opportunity and a strategic fit. Once Satyam's problem was solved, it was hoped that Maytas' payments can be delayed. But that was not to be. What followed in the last several days is common knowledge.

I would like the Board to know:

1. That neither myself, nor the Managing Director (including our spouses) sold any shares in the last eight years—excepting for a small proportion declared and sold for philanthropic purposes.
2. That in the last two years a net amount of Rs. 1,230 crore was arranged to Satyam (not reflected in the books of Satyam) to keep the operations going by resorting to pledging all the promoter shares and raising funds from known sources by giving all kinds of assurances (Statement enclosed, only to the members of the board).

Significant dividend payments, acquisitions, capital expenditure to provide for growth did not help matters. Every attempt was made to keep the wheel moving and to ensure prompt payment of salaries to the associates. The last straw was the selling of most of the pledged share by the lenders on account of margin triggers.

3. That neither me, nor the Managing Director took even one rupee/dollar from the company and have not benefitted in financial terms on account of the inflated results.

Fabricated Balance Sheet and Income Statement of Satyam: As of September 30, 2008

Table-2 “Income Statement”

Description	Actual	Reported	Difference
Cash and Bank Balances	321	5,361	5,040
Accrued Interest on bank FDs	Nil	376.5	376
Understated Liability	1230	None	1230
Overstated Debtors	2161	2651	490
Total	Nil	Nil	7136
Revenues (Q2 FY 2009)	2112	2700	588
Operating Profits	61	649	588

Source- Annual Report of Saytam

Stake Sale by Promoters of Satyam:

Table-3 “Statement”

Name of Promoters	No. of Shares Sold	Money Earned Rs.(crs)
B. Ramalinga Raju	9,825,000	773.42
B. Rama Raju	11,318,500	894.32
B. Suryanarayana Raju	111,000	12.81
B. Nandini Raju	4,047,000	327.59
B. Radha	3,873,500	313.55
B. Jhansi Rani	100,000	11.25
B. Pritam Teja	942,250	49.01
B. Rama Raju (Jr.)	934,250	48.62
Maytas Infra Ltd (Satyam Construction Ltd.)	0	-
B. Satyanarayana Raju	0	-
B. Appal Anarsamma	0	-
Elem Investments Pvt. Ltd	2,547,708	181.29
Fincity Investments Pvt. Ltd	2,530,400	180.41
Highgrace Investments Pvt. Ltd	2,530,332	170.83
Veeyes Investments Pvt. Ltd	57,500	71.79
Other Individuals connected to investment co	68,000	515.58
Off market transfers by investment co’s in the year 2001 (value estimated)	190,000	78.29
Promoters Group Total	39,075,440	3,029.67

Source- Based on Scholar Work

LIABILITY OF RAMALINGA RAJU AS A DIRECTOR

CRIMINAL CHARGES AGAINST RAJU:

Satyam founder Ramalinga Raju and his brother Rama Raju were arrested as part of the crackdown by state authorities and the central government, which disbanded the tainted IT firm's board on a day of fast-paced developments.

Raju was arrested and has been booked in a case of financial irregularities, Additional Director General of CB-CID A.S. Shivnarayan said minutes after the police action. —Both are in our custody. A case has been registered and we will produce them before the court within 24 hours, Kaumudi told reporters outside the office Director General of Police, Andhra Pradesh. The 54-year-old Raju, who stepped down as chairman after admitting to the fraud and Rama Raju, who resigned as CEO and MD of the company, were arrested under five sections of the Indian Penal Code section 120B for criminal conspiracy, section 420 for cheating, section 409 for criminal breach of trust, section 468 for forgery and also section 471 for falsification of records. All the charges are non-bailable offences.

The Auditors Role and Factors Contributing to Fraud:

Global auditing firm, PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), audited Satyam's books from June 2000 until the discovery of the fraud in 2009. Several commentators criticized PwC harshly for failing to detect the fraud (Winkler, 2010). Indeed, PwC signed Satyam's financial statements and was responsible for the numbers under the Indian law. One particularly troubling item concerned the \$1.04 billion that Satyam claimed to have on its balance sheet in "non-interest-bearing" deposits. According to accounting professionals, "any reasonable company would have either invested the money into an interest-bearing account, or returned the excess cash to the shareholders. The large amount of cash thus should have been a 'red-flag' for the auditors that further verification and testing was necessary.

Furthermore, it appears that the auditors did not independently verify with the banks in which Satyam claimed to have deposits" (Kahn, 2009). Additionally, the Satyam fraud went on for a number of years and involved both the manipulation of balance sheets and income statements. Whenever Satyam needed more income to meet analyst estimates, it simply created 'fictitious' sources and it did so numerous times, without the auditors ever discovering the fraud. Furthermore, PwC audited the company for nearly 9 years and did not uncover the fraud, whereas Merrill Lynch discovered the fraud as part of its due diligence in merely 10 days Missing these "red-flags" implied either that the auditors were grossly inept or in collusion with the company in committing the fraud.

PWC initially asserted that it performed all of the company's audits in accordance with applicable auditing standards. A point has also been raised about the increase in audit fee. A reference to the figures of audit fee in comparison with total income over a period of time may be pertinent. Over a period of four years, 2004-05 to 2007-08, the audit fee increased by 5.7 times, whereas total income increased by 2.47 times during the same period. Nevertheless, it is difficult to draw any conclusion as to whether the increase in audit fee was justified or not. Suspiciously, Satyam also paid PwC twice what other firms would charge for the audit, which raises questions about whether PwC was complicit in the fraud.

Acquisition by Mahindra Group:

On 13 April 2009, via a formal public auction process, a 46% stake in Satyam was purchased by Mahindra & Mahindra owned company Tech Mahindra, as part of its diversification strategy. Effective July 2009, Satyam rebranded its services under the new Mahindra management as "Mahindra Satyam". After a delay due to tax issues Tech Mahindra announced its merger with Mahindra Satyam on 21 March 2012, after the board of two companies gave the approval. The companies are merged legally on 25 June 2013.

Aftermath of Satyam Scandals:

Ramalinga Raju along with 2 other accused of the scandal, had been granted bail from Supreme court on 4 November 2011 as the investigation agency CBI failed to file the charge sheet even after more than 33 months Raju being arrested.

Raju had appointed a task force to address the Maytas situation in the last few days before revealing the news of the accounting fraud. After the scandal broke, the then-board members elected Ram Mynampati to be Satyam's interim CEO. Mynampati's statement on Satyam's website said:

"We are obviously shocked by the contents of the letter. The senior leaders of Satyam stand united in their commitment to customers, associates, suppliers and all shareholders. We have gathered together at Hyderabad to strategize the way forward in light of this startling revelation."

On 10 January 2009, the Company Law Board decided to bar the current board of Satyam from functioning and appoint 10 nominal directors. "The current board has failed to do what they are supposed to do. The credibility of the IT industry should not be allowed to suffer." said Corporate Affairs Minister Prem Chand Gupta. Chartered accountants regulator ICAI issued show-cause notice to Satyam's auditor PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC) on the accounts fudging. "We have asked PwC to reply within 21 days," ICAI President Ved Jain said.

On the same day, the Crime Investigation Department (CID) team picked up Vadlamani Srinivas, Satyam's then-CFO, for questioning. He was arrested later and kept in judicial custody.

On 11 January 2009, the government nominated noted banker **Deepak Parekh**, former **NASSCOM** chief **Kiran Karnik** and former SEBI member C. Achuthan to Satyam's board.

Analysts in India have termed the Satyam scandal India's own Enron scandal. Some social commentators see it more as a part of a broader problem relating to India's family-owned corporate environment.

Immediately following the news, Merrill Lynch (now a part of Bank of America) and State Farm Insurance terminated its engagement with the company. Also, Credit Suisse suspended

its coverage of Satyam. It was also reported that Satyam's auditing firm PricewaterhouseCoopers will be scrutinized for complicity in this scandal. SEBI, the stock market regulator, also said that, if found guilty, its license to work in India may be revoked. Satyam was the 2008 winner of the coveted Golden Peacock Award for Corporate Governance under Risk Management and Compliance Issues, which was stripped from them in the aftermath of the scandal. The New York Stock Exchange has halted trading in Satyam stock as of 7 January 2009. India's National Stock Exchange has announced that it will remove Satyam from its S&P CNX Nifty 50-share index on 12 January. The founder of Satyam was arrested two days after he admitted to falsifying the firm's accounts. Ramalinga Raju is charged with several offences, including criminal conspiracy, breach of trust, and forgery.

Satyam's shares fell to 11.50 rupees on 10 January 2009, their lowest level since March 1998, compared to a high of 544 rupees in 2008. In New York Stock Exchange Satyam shares peaked in 2008 at US\$29.10; by March 2009 they were trading around US\$1.80.

The Indian Government has stated that it may provide temporary direct or indirect liquidity support to the company. However, whether employment will continue at pre-crisis levels, particularly for new recruits, is questionable

On 14 January 2009, Price Waterhouse, the Indian division of PricewaterhouseCoopers, announced that its reliance on potentially false information provided by the management of Satyam may have rendered its audit reports "inaccurate and unreliable".

On 22 January 2009, CID told in court that the actual number of employees is only 40,000 and not 53,000 as reported earlier and that Mr. Raju had been allegedly withdrawing 200 million every month for paying these 13,000 non-existent employees.

The Indian government designated A. S. Murthy to become the new CEO of Satyam effective 5 February 2009. Special advisors were also appointed, Homi Khusrokhhan of Tata Chemicals and Chartered Accountant Partho Datta.

On 15 September 2014, the special CBI court hearing the case has asked the concerned parties to appear before the court on 27 October. Date of judgment will be indicated later on that day.

On 9 April 2015: Raju and nine others found guilty of collaborating to inflate the company's revenue, falsifying accounts and income tax returns and fabricating invoices among other things and sentenced seven years imprisonment by Hyderabad court. Raju and his brother were also fined by the court 55 million rupees each.

**Stock Charting of Satyam from December 2008 to January 2009:
Table-4 “Fall From GRACE Statement”**

Source- Based on Scholar Work

Investigation: Criminal, Civil Charges and Victims:

The investigation that followed the revelation of the fraud has led to charges against several different groups of people involved with Satyam. Indian authorities arrested Mr. Raju, Mr. Raju's brother, B. Ramu Raju, its former managing director, Srinivas Vdlamani, the company's head of internal audit, and its CFO on criminal charges of fraud. Indian authorities also arrested and charged several of the company's auditors (PwC) with fraud. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI) ruled that "the CFO and the auditor were guilty of professional misconduct."

The CBI is also in the course of investigating the CEO's overseas assets. There were also several civil charges filed in the U.S. against Satyam by the holders of its ADRs. The Investigation also implicated several Indian politicians. Both civil and criminal litigation cases continue in India and civil litigation continues in the United States. Some of the main victims, according to Manoharan (2011), were:

- **Employees** of Satyam spent anxious moments and sleep-less nights as they faced non-payment of salaries, project cancellations, layoffs and equally-bleak prospects of outside employment Opportunities. They were stranded in many ways: morally, financially, legally, and socially.
- **Clients** of Satyam expressed loss of trust and reviewed their contracts, preferring to go with other competitors. Several global clients, like Cisco, Telstra and World Bank cancelled their contracts with the Satyam. "Customers were shocked and worried about the project continuity, confidentiality and cost overrun."
- **Shareholders** lost their valuable investments and there was doubt about revival of India, as a preferred investment destination. The VC and MD of Mahindra, in a statement, said that the

Development had “resulted in incalculable and unjustifiable damage to Brand India and Brand-IT, in particular.”

- **Bankers** were concerned about recovery of financial and non-financial exposure and recalled facilities.
- **Indian Government** was worried about its image of the nation and IT-sector affecting faith to invest, or to do business in the country.

In the aftermath of Satyam, India’s markets recovered and Satyam now lives on. India’s stock market is currently trading near record highs, as it appears that a global economic recovery is taking place. Civil litigation and criminal charges continue against Satyam. Tech Mahindra purchased 51% of Satyam on April 16, 2009, successfully saving the firm from a complete collapse. As Winkler states (2010), “With the right changes, India can minimize the rate and size of accounting fraud in the Indian capital markets.”

Regulatory CG Reforms in India and Lessons Learned at Satyam

India immediately portrayed the Satyam scandal as an aberration to try to salvage the remaining confidence in its capital markets. Several commentators, however, claimed that the scandal was not an aberration, but a sign of governance issues in India. After the Satyam scandal, investors and regulators called for strengthening the regulatory environment in the securities markets. In response to the scandal, the SEBI revised CG requirements as well as financial reporting requirements for publicly traded corporations listed in the country. The SEBI also strengthened its commitment to the adoption of International Financial Accounting Reporting Standards (IFRS). In addition, the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) is devising a new Corporate Code and is considering changing the securities laws to make it easier for shareholders to bring class action lawsuits. Some of the recent CG reforms undertaken in India are:

(a) Independent Directors: The Satyam scandal reinforced the Indian regulators commitment to continue the process of CG reform. Even before the Satyam scandal broke, India was in the process of updating its 1956 Companies Act, which sets out key Indian CG rules. The SEBI is considering several proposals ranging from mandating increased due diligence on transactions to increasing personal liability of board members. If reform continues on its current course, reform within the 1956 Companies Act will make it easier for shareholders to sue officers and directors of corporations. The SEBI is also considering making publicly listed companies carry director and officer liability insurance to protect shareholders from damages. Additionally, the SEBI proposed creating a law that provides whistleblowers with protection for reporting fraudulent activity. Finally, the SEBI revised takeover regulations to increase disclosure in takeovers.

(b) Disclosure of Pledged Securities: After Satyam, the SEBI increased disclosure obligations of promoters and controlling shareholders. Before the Satyam scandal, promoters and controlling shareholders were not required to disclose to investors if they had pledged their stock. Two weeks after Satyam’s collapse, the SEBI made it mandatory for controlling shareholders to disclose any share pledges.

(c) Increased Financial Accounting Disclosures: The SEBI also recently proposed requiring companies to disclose their balance sheet positions twice a year. Pre-Satyam, the regulations only required disclosure of balance sheet positions once a year. The increased reporting of companies’ balance sheets will provide investors with more information on the stability of a company’s financial position. Increasing both the frequency and detail of disclosure will help provide for a more robust market check—e.g. investors will be able to police companies better and pay more attention to accounting irregularities. For example, increased frequency of disclosure of Satyam’s balance sheet could have led to an investor discovering, and pressing the board to investigate, the claimed large cash deposits in non-interest bearing accounts more quickly.

(d) IFRS (Adoption of International Standards): Satyam strengthened India’s commitment to adopting International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) by 2011. Currently, Indian Generally Accepted Accounting Practices (GAAP) and the IFRS differ significantly. Globally, more and more countries are moving towards IFRS, as currently more than 100 countries require, permit, or are converting to IFRS. Adopting IFRS will facilitate investor comparisons of financial performance across country lines and will increase confidence in the accounting numbers

(e) Creation of New Corporate Code by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs: In addition to the new SEBI regulatory requirements, the Indian Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) is drafting a new corporate code for Indian publicly listed companies. The new code will apply along with the regulatory obligations imposed by the SEBI. Adherence to the Code will be voluntary; however, every company that deviates from the codes requirements must disclose the deviations to the ministry.

The MCA anticipates that the new code will impose more stringent disclosure obligations than the SEBI currently requires. The MCA recently proposed a new law that would make it easier for Indian investors to form “class action” lawsuits against fraudulent actors in the company. Indian Corporate Affairs Minister, Salman Khushid, stated that he envisioned drafting the law to provide investors with a claim similar to the shareholder derivative suit that U.S. law permits. Indian law currently creates obstacles to investors filing class action lawsuits. The MCA hopes that this new law will provide Indian citizens with the confidence to invest in the financial markets.

Satyam grossly violated all rules of corporate governance (Chakrabarti, 2008). The Satyam scam had been the example for following “poor” CG practices. It had failed to show good relation with the shareholders and employees. As Kahn (2009) stated, “CG issue at Satyam

arose because of non-fulfillment of obligation of the company towards the various stakeholders. Of specific interest are the following: distinguishing the roles of board and management; separation of the roles of the CEO and chairman; appointment to the board; directors and executive compensation; protection of shareholders rights and their executives.” In fact, shareholders never had the opportunity to give their consent prior to the announcement of the Matyas deal and ‘falsified’ documents with grossly ‘inflated’ financial reports were delivered to them.

Ultimately, shareholders were at a loss and felt cheated. Surely, questions about management’s credibility were raised, in addition to the non-payment of advance taxes to the government. Together, these issues raise questions about Satyam’s financial health. According to Sharma (), “Some of the steps which could be taken to strengthen corporate governance are: have in all listed companies a code on ethics; independent regulatory body on the lines of the Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB) of USA; rotation of external auditors in non-financial institutions; Reform Audit Education; split offices of chairman and CEO; encourage competent directors; abolish practice of nominating independent directors, exempt independent directors from vicarious liability; provide insurance cover to them; review the definition of independent director given in clause 49 of listing agreement; close supervision of rating agencies; superior Board practices, improve remuneration policy; legislative sanction to insider trading laws; introduce new audit standards; make audit committee strictly independent; prohibit political funding; install whistleblower system; introduce class action suit & compensation; make CSR compliance a mandatory provision; have in place permanent PPP system, and enhance criminal and civil penalties.”

The 2009 Satyam scandal in India highlighted the nefarious potential of an improperly governed corporate leader. As the fallout continues, and the effects were felt throughout the global economy, the prevailing hope is that some good can come from the scandal in terms of lessons learned (Behan, 2009).

Here are some lessons learned from the Satyam Scandal:

- **Investigate All Inaccuracies:** The fraud scheme at Satyam started very small, eventually growing into \$276 million white-elephant in the room. Indeed, a lot of fraud schemes initially start out small, with the perpetrator thinking that small changes here and there would not make a big difference, and is less likely to be detected. This sends a message to a lot of companies: if your accounts are not balancing, or if something seems inaccurate (even just a tiny bit), it is worth investigating. Dividing responsibilities across a team of people makes it easier to detect irregularities or misappropriated funds.
- **Ruined reputations:** Fraud does not just look bad on a company; it looks bad on the whole industry and a country. “India’s biggest corporate scandal in memory threatens future foreign investment flows into Asia’s third-largest economy and casts a cloud over growth in its once-

booming outsourcing sector. The news sent Indian equity markets into a tail-spin, with Bombay's main benchmark index tumbling 7.3% and the Indian rupee fell" (IMF, 2010). Now, because of the Satyam scandal, Indian rivals will come under greater scrutiny by the regulators, investors and customers.

- **Corporate Governance needs to be stronger:** The Satyam case is just another example supporting the need for stronger CG. All public-companies must be careful when selecting executives and top-level managers. These are the people who set the tone for the company: if there is corruption at the top, it is bound to trickle-down. Also, separate the role of CEO and Chairman of the Board. Splitting up the roles, thus, helps avoid situations like the one at Satyam.

The Satyam Computer Services' scandal brought to light the importance of ethics and its relevance to corporate culture. The fraud committed by the founders of Satyam is a testament to the fact that "the science of conduct" is swayed in large by human greed, ambition, and hunger for power, money, fame and glory. Scandals from Enron to the recent financial crisis have time and time again proven that there is a need for good conduct based on strong ethics. Not surprising, such frauds can happen, at any time, all over the world. Satyam fraud spurred the government of India to tighten CG norms to prevent recurrence of similar frauds in the near future. The government took prompt actions to protect the interest of the investors and safeguard the credibility of India and the nation's image across the world.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION:

The Satyam episode has sparked a big debate on whether India possesses adequate laws and guidelines for corporate governance. Risk managers say that while India has no dearth of such provisions in various enactments, the real issue emanates from the ability to follow these provisions in spirit and the means to monitor and enforce the same. The law makers in India, they believe, need to ascertain the merits of encouraging a principle-based approach (like in the case of the combined code in the UK) to compliance - where the nature, size and complexities of a business govern compliance and disclosures - instead of a standard rules based approach for universal compliance (like in the US). The Satyam fiasco has called into review the Corporate Governance in India. The problem in India relates to the fact that we have been adopting Corporate Governance rather than formulating our own. The watchdog of investors SEBI was instituted as a body under SEBI ACT, 1992.

Thus it has been only 16 years since a watchdog for the investors has been incorporated. In the past 16 years this is the first major scam which has affected Corporate Governance in India and the concept of India Inc. as a whole. In India, guidelines for corporate governance are provided in clause 49 of the listing agreement and also in various sections of the Companies Act. Industry experts hold view that once appointed, the performance and contributions of these directors should be monitored and evaluated objectively with peer reviews serving as a means of such evaluations.

The Satyam scandal has, ironically, uncovered the second most populated country in the world, of having a problem with numbers in terms of finding the requisite number of directors who can exercise their independence while influencing decisions of the board. The challenge for India Inc is to come out of the mindset that only well known personalities can be nominated as independent directors. The role of Independent Directors has again been brought under preview however there is still a conflict between SEBI and Company Bills, 2008 as to the percentage of Independent Directors on the board.

The shareholders of a company place very high reliance on the auditor's report, which apparently shows the true and fair view of the accounts of a company. The auditors should perform their duties with utmost care and vigilance to ensure that there are no illegal or improper transactions. But still, Satyam has happened. The role of the UICAI and MCA should now not just be confined to punishing Satyam's auditors, but they should also re-examine the present system to strengthen and intensify internal audit system. Some of such remedial steps, which may be taken, are as follows:

- 1). Appointment and remuneration of auditors should not be left to the companies they audit, as the fees can easily influence the auditor's report. A better option would be to pool in money and hand it over to the stock exchanges that can appoint auditors. This will make the auditors answerable to the bourses and not corporate executives.
- 2). Forensic auditors should be used to unearth evidence of wrongdoing, which needs a combined team of people from the police or the CBI, lawyers and audit professionals with an adversarial approach.
- 3). Other than forensic audits, even investigative audit techniques could be applied wherever major weaknesses in internal controls or their implementation are found. An investigator does not accept a stated fact as correct unless it is substantiated.
- 4). The professional firms should introduce partners' audit review and partner-rotation programs. This will also ensure healthy participation on the part of the partners.
- 5). The auditors should also ensure that the audit is conducted in accordance with the **Auditing and Assurance Standards (AAS)**, which are is benchmark on which the quality of audit performance can be measured, and any material departure should be disclosed. **AAS-4** talks about the Auditor's responsibility in considering fraud in audit of financial statement. Besides these, steps should be taken to ensure that the auditors are fulfilling their general duties of getting third party evidence, identifying and assessing the risk of material misstatement in financial statement due to fraud, contacting major customers/suppliers etc. These steps will bring in light fraud but won't stop them.

Strong laws have never deterred criminals. But if there is a comprehensive paperwork to support it, over a period of time, it can be detected by common sense approach instead of mechanical. Meanwhile many feel that if the two pending bills in Parliament related to

company affairs- The Companies Bill 2008 and Limited Liability Partners Act were passed earlier, stringent action could have been taken against corporate fraudsters and protect the interest of shareholders.

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